

IMPORTANCE OF INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL STANDARDS IN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF AGRICULTURE

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Abstract. This article describes the rapid development of production, modernization and diversification of industry, increasing the competitiveness of light industry products by harmonizing international standards with agricultural standards.

Keywords: competitiveness, quality management system, standardization, certification, modernization, transformation.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada xalqaro standartlar bilan qishloq xo'jaligiga oid standartlarni uyg'unlashtirish orqali ishlab chiqarishni jadal rivojlantirish, sanoatni modernizatsiya va diversifikatsiya qilish, yengil sanoat mahsulotlari raqobatbardoshligini oshirish keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: raqobatbardoshlik, sifat menejmenti tizimi, standartlash, sertifikatlash, modernizatsiya, devirsifikatsiya.

АННОТАЦИЯ В статье описывается стремительное развитие производства, модернизация и диверсификация промышленности, повышение конкурентоспособности продукции легкой промышленности за счет гармонизации международных стандартов с сельскохозяйственными стандартами.

Ключевые слова: конкурентоспособность, система менеджмента качества, стандартизация, сертификация, модернизация, трансформация.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the role of standardization is increasing as one of the main elements of solving global problems of world development. The formation of uniform

standards will help the active spread of environmental protection technologies, as well as risk assessment that increases the level of safety, production processes and energy efficiency. In this regard, it can be said that standards are an important tool for improvement.

On September 6, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev held a meeting dedicated to the priorities of the development of agriculture in 2020-2030.

Our country has great potential in agriculture. Many issues are related to this sector, from the abundance of our markets and the abundance of food for our people to earning additional income from exports.

In the following years, a number of works were carried out on the reform of agriculture and the introduction of market mechanisms. The interest increased as a result of the almost 3-fold increase in public procurement prices. Cotton and grain farming has become a real source of income, not a pest.

76 cotton-textile clusters were established in order to introduce new technologies and innovations, increase labor productivity and wages.

This year alone, a new water-saving irrigation system was introduced on 25,000 hectares of cotton fields. Efforts to bring 1,100,000 hectares of abandoned land back into use have begun.

These are, of course, good results, but these actions are the first stage of reforms.

Our President is thinking not only of today, but also of tomorrow, and is setting the task of raising the reforms to a new level with a long view. For this purpose, the strategy of agricultural development for 2020-2030 is being developed. This will be the main growth point, "driver" of our economy. Thousands of jobs will be created, people's income will increase.

Important tasks necessary for the implementation of this strategy were determined at the meeting.

First of all, it was noted that it is necessary to keep an accurate account of agricultural lands and improve their use. Based on this, the "Yergeodezkadastr"

committee was instructed to complete the land registration works in all regions of the republic by the end of 2021, to create a single electronic database for land accounting.

As noted, landowners must have full faith in the future in order to pursue productivity and perennial fruit production. Therefore, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan has reviewed the legislation and emphasized the need to ensure a transparent system of land allocation and the guarantee of the right to land.

Proper use of water in agriculture is also a very important issue. According to the analysis, although billions of cubic meters of water are directed to cultivated areas in our country, only 60% of it reaches crops, 40% is lost in irrigation systems and during irrigation.

According to estimates of the World Water Resources Institute, by 2040, Uzbekistan may be among 33 countries with extreme water shortages.

Therefore, the head of our state paid special attention to this issue, emphasized the need to increase the efficiency of water use and keep its account, to introduce water-saving technologies on an area of 200,000 hectares every year. It was said that these directions should be reflected in the strategy being developed.

While discussing the issues of state support for agriculture and improvement of the state procurement system, it was pointed out that the main part of the budget funds should be spent on increasing land productivity, introducing water-saving technologies, and developing science.

Special importance was paid to the issues of increasing the export potential of the industry and increasing the volume of production of value-added products, and the world experience in this regard was analyzed.

For example, 1 hectare of land in Turkey produces 2,000 dollars worth of produce, 8,000 dollars in Egypt, and 12,000 dollars in Israel. In Uzbekistan, this indicator does not exceed 300 dollars. Our products are not able to compete in the foreign market due to the fact that it is not always possible to supply goods of the same standard.

At the meeting, officials were given tasks to introduce the product certification system based on the standards of the European Union, East Asia and Arab countries.

In this regard, it was noted that real estates are also a big reserve, and it is necessary to widely introduce logistics service and cooperation system in local areas based on the principle of "one neighborhood - one product".

There are also shortcomings in terms of service. For example, in this system, due to the lack of competition, the price of services is high, and the product manufacturer has no choice.

Therefore, it was emphasized that it is necessary to increase the types of services based on public-private partnership in the field of mineral fertilizers, plant protection, equipment and other services, and to establish the activities of private enterprises.

By the end of 2020, it is necessary to complete the work of rapid and reliable assessment of the actual condition of the soil and crops through space sensing of the earth, which began this year. This system provides complete information about the vegetation process, soil reclamation condition and the amount of mineralization, moisture level, and allows to increase productivity by 25-30 percent.

Officials were given tasks to introduce a complete digitization system of processes from crop placement to sale.

First of all, qualified personnel are needed to effectively organize the execution of the above tasks. On the basis of international experience, it was noted the importance of implementing a new method of teaching in higher educational institutions specialized in the field, organizing mobile training classes and seminars with the participation of professors and teachers.

In scientific research institutes, instructions were also given on the creation of livestock breeds suitable for early product types and regional climate, commercialization of scientific developments.

In general, the new strategy aims to ensure food security by introducing market mechanisms to agriculture, establishing science-based production, increasing exports, and increasing per capita output. how many times it serves to increase.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SUBJECT.

In the process of covering this article SH.M. Mirziyoyev's works were identified as a methodological source. In this article, the method of logicity, historicity, consistency, and objectivity of scientific knowledge was used, and descriptive and comparative methods were used to illuminate the topic. In the process of research, the issue of rapid development of production by harmonizing international standards with agricultural standards was objectively analyzed.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS. The application of international standards and the use of national standards of developed countries are among the priority directions in the field of standardization in our country. In accordance with Article 6 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Standardization" and for more effective use of standards taking into account the technical level of technology and equipment, the "Uzstandart" agency currently has more than 44,000 normative documents in its fund of normative documents. documents are collected. They include 8116 international standards, 20393 interstate standards, 8679 national standards of foreign countries, 1679 state standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 168 industry standards, 4692 technical conditions, 334 enterprise standards, and 198 management documents.

CONCLUSION The introduction of production by harmonizing international standards with agricultural standards leads to the fulfillment of quality goals, a reduction in the number of non-conformities as a result of audits, the ratio of preventive actions to corrective actions to eliminate potential problems, and an increase in product profitability. , leading to increased consumer satisfaction as well as increased agricultural productivity.

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